

Enhanced sensitivity of nasopharyngeal carcinoma cells to cisplatin by triptolide: *in vitro* analysis of synergistic effects and mechanisms

Pingping Sun¹, Jiajia Yan², Yao Zeng¹, Jie Chen², Shuxia Li²

¹ GCP office, The First Affiliated Hospital of Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China

² Department of Pharmacy, The First Affiliated Hospital of Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China

Corresponding author: Shuxia Li (lishuxia@mail.sysu.edu.cn)

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Abstract

Cisplatin (DDP) resistance severely limits the efficacy of chemotherapy for nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC). This study investigated the potential of triptolide (TPL) to enhance DDP sensitivity in human nasopharyngeal carcinoma CNE-1 cells and explored the underlying mechanisms. Apoptosis was assessed by Hoechst 33528 staining and flow cytometry. Gene and protein expression of Bcl-2 family members (Bcl-2 and Bax) and MAPK pathway activation (ERK1/2 and JNK) were analyzed using real-time PCR and western blotting. Our data revealed that TPL exerts concentration-dependent pro-apoptotic effects and synergistically augments the anti-proliferative effects of DDP on CNE-1 cells, with combined treatment inducing apoptosis more potently than either agent alone. The TPL+DDP group exhibited marked Bcl-2 suppression at both the transcriptional and translational levels, coupled with Bax upregulation at the transcriptional level compared with monotherapy, while Bax protein expression remained unchanged. Furthermore, TPL selectively activated MAPK signaling, significantly increasing phosphorylation of ERK1/2 and JNK, whereas no activation was observed for p38. Collectively, TPL enhances DDP sensitivity by modulating the Bcl-2/Bax balance and engaging ERK/JNK pathways, suggesting its clinical potential as a chemosensitizer in NPC treatment.

Keywords

cisplatin, nasopharyngeal carcinoma, sensitization, triptolide

Introduction

The number of new cases and deaths from nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) worldwide is projected to exceed 120,416 and 73,476, respectively, in 2022 (Filho et al. 2024). This disease imposes a significant global burden, and its incidence exhibits notable geographical variation – with a distinct predilection for populations in south-

ern China and Southeast Asia – further highlighting its impact on public health in these high-prevalence regions (Chen et al. 2019). Currently, cisplatin (DDP)-based radiotherapy and chemotherapy are the primary treatments for NPC (Blanchard et al. 2022). However, the emergence of drug resistance following prolonged use can substantially compromise overall therapeutic efficacy, potentially resulting in treatment failure. Although several improve-

ments have been achieved, the prognosis for NPC remains poor, with the 5-year survival rate after treatment ranging from 38–71% (Jia et al. 2006; Chen et al. 2019; Dwijayanti et al. 2020; Goshtasbi et al. 2021). Thus, overcoming drug resistance has become a critical priority for improving therapeutic outcomes in NPC.

To identify potential strategies for enhancing NPC treatment efficacy, triptolide (TPL), the main active component of the traditional Chinese herb *Tripterygium wilfordii* Hook.f., has attracted attention because of its prominent antitumor properties. TPL is a small-molecule drug (MW: 360.6; see Fig. 1 for the structure) that exhibits significant antitumor activity by inhibiting growth and inducing apoptosis in a wide range of human tumor cells, including melanoma, breast, bladder, gastric, liver, and colorectal cancers, at nanomolar concentrations (Wang et al. 2019; Song et al. 2022; Cai et al. 2023; Chen et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2024; Zhao et al. 2024). Importantly, previous studies have demonstrated that TPL exhibits clear cytotoxicity in nasopharyngeal carcinoma cells in vitro, suggesting its potential application in NPC treatment (Wang et al. 2019).

Figure 1. The structure of TPL.

However, the effect of TPL combined with DDP has not yet been reported. This study aimed to investigate whether TPL can inhibit cell proliferation and potentiate DDP in NPC, and to explore the potential mechanisms.

Materials and methods

Materials

Triptolide (TPL; National Institute for Pharmaceutical and Biological Products Control, China); RPMI-1640 medium (Gibco, USA); fetal bovine serum (Gibco, USA); MTT assay kit (Sigma, USA); Hoechst 33258 assay kit (Beyotime Biotechnology, China); Annexin V-PI Apoptosis Detection Kit (Beyotime Biotechnology, China); TRIzol reagent (Invitrogen, USA); PrimeScript RT reagent Kit and SYBR Premix Ex Taq (Takara, Japan); forward and reverse primers for β -actin, Bcl-2, and Bax (Invitrogen, USA); rabbit anti-human Bcl-2, Bax, p-JNK, and GAPDH antibodies (Cell Signaling Technology, USA); rabbit anti-human ERK1/2, p-ERK1/2, pp38, p38, and JNK antibodies (Ab-

cam, USA); HRP-conjugated goat anti-rabbit IgG (Abcam, USA); chemiluminescent substrate kit (Millipore, USA).

Cell culture

The human nasopharyngeal carcinoma CNE-1 cell line (kindly provided by the Otolaryngology Laboratory of the First Affiliated Hospital of Sun Yat-sen University) was cultured in RPMI-1640 medium supplemented with 10% (v/v) FBS, 100 U/mL penicillin, and 100 ng/mL streptomycin at 37 °C under 5% CO₂.

Cell viability assay

Cell viability was determined by MTT assay. Briefly, CNE-1 cells were seeded in 6-well plates (1.2×10^6 cells/mL) and allowed to adhere overnight. Two experimental sets were conducted: one with TPL (0, 2.5, 5, 10, 20, 50, and 100 ng/mL) incubated for 24, 48, or 72 h, and the other with 2.5 ng/mL TPL, 0.1 μ g/mL DDP, or their combination incubated for 24, 48, or 72 h (final DMSO $\leq 0.1\%$ in all wells), whereas control groups received 0.1% (v/v) DMSO. The final concentration of DMSO in all drug-containing plates was $\leq 0.1\%$. After incubation for 24, 48, or 72 h, the cells were treated with 20 μ L MTT solution (5 mg/mL) for 4 h, after which the culture medium was discarded. Formazan crystals were dissolved in 200 μ L DMSO per well, and the plates were shaken for 10 min. Absorbance was measured at 490 nm using a microplate reader. Viability was calculated as (A_{experimental} - A_{blank}) / (A_{control} - A_{blank}) $\times 100\%$. There were nine parallel samples at each dose level, and the experiment was repeated three times.

Hoechst 33258 staining

Clean coverslips were soaked in 70% ethanol for at least 5 min and rinsed three times with sterile PBS, followed by one rinse with cell culture medium. The coverslips were placed in six-well plates, and cells were seeded overnight to achieve approximately 50%–80% confluence.

Two sets of experiments were performed. In the first set, cells were treated with 2.5, 5, or 10 ng/mL TPL. In the second set, cells were treated with 2.5 ng/mL TPL, 0.1 μ g/mL DDP, or their combination. Each group included three replicate wells. After 48 h of treatment, the culture medium was completely aspirated, and 0.5 mL of fixative (4% paraformaldehyde) was added to each well for 10 min. The fixative was removed, and the cells were washed twice with PBS or 0.9% NaCl for 3 min each time. Subsequently, the cells were stained with 0.5 mL Hoechst 33258 solution for 5 min. Nuclear morphology was examined using fluorescence microscopy (excitation at 350 nm).

Cell cycle

Cells (2.0×10^5 /dish) were inoculated in six-well plates and allowed to adhere overnight, then exposed to varying doses

of TPL (2.5, 5, or 10 ng/mL) for 48 h. For cell cycle analysis, cells were fixed in 70% ethanol at 4 °C overnight, rinsed with prechilled PBS, and suspended in 250 µL of 0.5% Triton X-100. After incubation with RNase A (200 µg/mL) for 15 min at 37 °C, the cells were analyzed using a BD FACS-Calibur flow cytometer (USA). To examine apoptosis, cells were stained with propidium iodide (PI; 100 µg/mL) at 4 °C for 15 min before flow cytometric analysis.

Annexin V–PI assay

Apoptosis was evaluated using the Annexin V–PI assay according to the manufacturer's instructions. After 48 h of treatment with 2.5 ng/mL TPL, 0.1 µg/mL DDP, or their combination, cells were digested with 0.25% trypsin for 2 min. Cells were washed twice with PBS for 3 min each time, centrifuged at 800 rpm for 3 min, and the supernatant was discarded. The cells were then stained with 5 µL Annexin V–FITC. Flow cytometry was performed to detect Annexin V–FITC and PI (Ex = 488 nm, Em = 530 nm).

Reverse transcription–quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT–qPCR)

CNE-1 cells were treated with 2.5 ng/mL TPL, 0.1 µg/mL DDP, or their combination for 48 h. Total RNA was extracted using TRIzol reagent according to the manufacturer's protocol. RNA was reverse transcribed using the PrimeScript RT reagent Kit (Takara), and quantitative PCR was performed on a 7500 Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems, USA). The amplification conditions were as follows: 95 °C for 30 s, followed by 95 °C for 5 min and 60 °C for 30 s, and a final cycle of 95 °C for 15 s, 60 °C for 1 min, and 95 °C for 15 s. The primer sequences were as follows: Bcl-2 forward 5'-TGGCCTTCTTGCG-GGAGTA-3'; Bcl-2 reverse 5'-TGGCCAGGTCAGGTA-AA-3'; Bax forward 5'-TTGCTTCAGGGTTTCTCCA-3'; Bax reverse 5'-AGACACTCGCTCTTCTTG-3'; β -actin forward 5'-GGAGATACTGCCTGGCTCTA-3'; β -actin reverse 5'-GATCATCGTACTCCTTGCTG-3'. Relative mRNA expression levels of Bcl-2 and Bax were normalized to β -actin, and data were analyzed using the $\Delta\Delta$ Ct method.

Western blot analysis

After 48 h of treatment with 2.5 ng/mL TPL, 0.1 µg/mL DDP, or their combination (three replicate wells per group), cells were collected for protein extraction and quantification. Proteins (30 µg per sample) were mixed with loading buffer, and 15 µL was loaded into each well of a 5%–12% SDS–polyacrylamide gel, followed by electrophoresis at 80–100 V using a Mini-PROTEAN 3 Electrophoresis System (Bio-Rad, USA). Proteins were then transferred to a PVDF membrane at 100 V for 75 min using a Mini Trans-Blot Transfer System (Bio-Rad, USA). Membranes were blocked with 1% skim milk powder dis-

solved in TBST at room temperature for 1 h and incubated overnight at 4 °C with primary antibodies against Bcl-2, Bax, GAPDH, p-ERK1/2, ERK1/2, p-JNK, and p-p38 (all diluted 1:2000), JNK (1:500), or p38 (1:400). After washing three times with TBST for 5 min each, membranes were incubated with HRP-conjugated goat anti-rabbit IgG (1:1000) for 1 h. Protein bands were visualized using a chemiluminescent substrate kit, with GAPDH used as the loading control. Images were developed using an automatic X-ray film processor.

Statistical analysis

Data are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 16.0 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, United States). The appropriateness of each test was determined based on the study design and data characteristics. An unpaired Student's *t*-test was used for comparisons between two independent groups when assumptions of normality and equal variance were met, as verified by the Shapiro–Wilk test and Levene's test, respectively. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's post hoc test was applied for multiple comparisons among three or more independent groups, ensuring accurate detection of intergroup differences while controlling for type I error. Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

Results

Triptolide induces concentration-dependent cytotoxicity, cell cycle arrest, and apoptosis in CNE-1 cells

The effect of TPL on CNE-1 cell viability was examined by exposing cells to increasing concentrations of TPL (2.5–100 ng/mL) for 24, 48, and 72 h. As shown in Fig. 2A, TPL-induced loss of cell viability exhibited time- and concentration-dependent trends. To further investigate the effects of TPL on the cell cycle and apoptosis, CNE-1 cells were treated with increasing concentrations of TPL (2.5, 5, and 10 ng/mL) for 48 h. Nuclear morphology was assessed using Hoechst 33258 staining (Fig. 2B), a hallmark of apoptosis. The results showed that increasing TPL concentrations led to a marked increase in nuclear condensation and fragmentation, as indicated by bright blue condensed nuclei. Cell cycle analysis (Fig. 2C, D), which evaluated cell cycle distribution and apoptotic sub-G1 populations, revealed a concentration-dependent increase in the proportion of cells in the sub-G1 phase following TPL treatment ($P < 0.05$). Consistent with these findings, Annexin V/PI staining (Fig. 2E, F), a standard flow cytometric method for apoptosis quantification, demonstrated that TPL promoted apoptosis in a concentration-dependent manner ($P < 0.05$). Based on these results, 2.5 ng/mL TPL was selected for subsequent experiments.

Figure 2. TPL exerted concentration-dependent effects on cell viability, nuclear morphology, cell cycle distribution, and apoptosis in CNE-1 cells. **A.** Cell viability assay; **B.** Hoechst 33258 staining; **C, D.** Cell cycle analysis by flow cytometry; **E, F.** Apoptosis detection via Annexin V/PI staining. $n = 3$. *Compared with control, $P < 0.05$.

TPL synergizes with DDP to inhibit CNE-1 cell proliferation and enhance apoptosis in CNE-1 cells

To investigate the potential synergistic effects of TPL and DDP on CNE-1 cells, cells were treated with 2.5 ng/mL

TPL and/or 1 μ g/mL DDP for 24, 48, and 72 h. As shown in Fig. 3A, combined treatment with TPL and DDP produced a greater antiproliferative effect than treatment with TPL or DDP alone ($P < 0.05$). This inhibitory effect increased in a time-dependent manner, evidenced by bright blue condensed nuclei. A marked increase in

Figure 3. TPL synergistically enhanced the efficacy of DDP in inhibiting cell viability and potentiating apoptosis in CNE-1 cells. **A.** Cell viability at 24, 48, and 72 h; **B.** Hoechst staining; **C, D.** Annexin V/PI staining. $n = 3$. *Compared with control, $P < 0.05$. #Compared with DDP, $P < 0.05$.

apoptotic cells was observed in the TPL+DDP group compared with the DDP-alone group. Furthermore, apoptosis induced by TPL and DDP was assessed using the Annexin V–FITC/PI assay. As illustrated in Fig. 3C, D, the proportion of apoptotic CNE-1 cells was 72.74% in the DDP-alone group, 14.30% in the TPL-alone group, and 92.93% in the TPL+DDP group, indicating that combined treatment induced a greater apoptotic response than either agent alone.

TPL and DDP induce CNE-1 cell apoptosis through Bcl-2 family proteins

Bcl-2 and Bax are members of the Bcl-2 family, which have the capacity to negatively and positively regulate mitochondrial events associated with apoptotic cell death. To explore the mechanism of apoptosis induced by TPL and DDP in CNE-1 cells, mRNA and protein expression levels of Bcl-2 and Bax were detected using real-time quantitative PCR and western blotting, respectively, with β -actin used as the control. As shown in Fig. 4A, Bax

mRNA expression was significantly higher in the TPL, DDP, and TPL+DDP groups than in the control group, with increases of 213%, 317%, and 582%, respectively ($P < 0.05$). Conversely, Bcl-2 mRNA expression in the DDP and TPL+DDP groups significantly decreased to 47% and 51%, respectively, compared with the control group ($P < 0.05$). In addition, the Bcl-2/Bax ratio in the TPL, DDP, and TPL+DDP groups significantly decreased to 45%, 15%, and 9%, respectively, compared with the control group ($P < 0.05$). Compared with the DDP group, the TPL+DDP group showed a more pronounced increase in Bax mRNA expression and a greater decrease in Bcl-2 mRNA expression ($P < 0.05$). To assess protein expression, western blot analysis was performed. As shown in Fig. 4B, C, Bcl-2 protein levels were significantly reduced in the TPL, DDP, and TPL+DDP groups compared with the control group ($P < 0.05$). In contrast, no significant changes in Bax protein expression were observed among the groups. Consequently, the Bcl-2/Bax ratio was markedly decreased in the TPL+DDP group compared with the control group ($P < 0.05$) and the DDP group (# $P <$

Figure 4. The synergistic apoptosis induced by TPL and DDP is mediated via the Bcl-2 family of proteins. **A.** Bcl-2 and Bax mRNA levels analyzed by RT-qPCR; **B, C.** Bcl-2 and Bax protein levels analyzed by western blotting. $n = 3$. *Compared with control, $P < 0.05$. #Compared with DDP, $P < 0.05$.

0.05), indicating a pro-apoptotic shift in the balance of these apoptosis-regulatory proteins.

MAPK signaling pathway is involved in TPL-induced DDP sensitivity in CNE-1 cells

There are three types of mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) families in humans: extracellular signal-regulated kinases (ERK1/2), the p38 kinase family (p38), and c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK), which play vital roles in apoptosis, cell proliferation, and differentiation (Kim and Choi 2010; Yue and Lopez 2020). The induction of phosphorylated ERK, JNK, and p38, which activates the MAPK signaling pathway, has the capacity to trigger apoptosis in cancer cells (Junttila et al. 2008; Saahene et al. 2021; Cheng et al. 2022). Therefore, the effects of TPL on the phosphorylation status of MAPK family proteins, including ERK, JNK, and p38, were examined by western blotting. As shown in Fig. 5, both the TPL and DDP groups significantly increased the protein expression levels of p-ERK1/2 and p-JNK ($P < 0.05$). Compared with the TPL and DDP groups, the TPL+DDP group exhibited statistically significant increases in p-ERK1 (361%), p-ERK2 (235%), and p-JNK (329%) protein levels, indicating a more pronounced effect. Furthermore, the phosphorylation level of p-p38 protein was examined, and the results indicated no significant difference between the experimental groups and the control group, suggesting that TPL and DDP do not affect p38 protein expression. These results suggest that TPL enhances cellular sensitivity to DDP by activating ERK and JNK phosphorylation in the MAPK pathway, but not p38.

Figure 5. Combined effect of TPL and DDP on the expression of p-ERK1/2, p-JNK, and p-p38 in CNE-1 cells. The CNE-1 cells were treated with 2.5 ng/mL TPL and/or 1 μ g/mL DDP for 48 h. Protein expression levels were expressed as fold changes relative to vehicle-treated control cells, which were set as 1-fold. **A.** Relative expression levels of p-ERK1/2, p-JNK, and p-p38 normalized to GAPDH; **B.** protein expression levels of p-ERK1/2, p-JNK, and p-p38 detected by western blotting. $n = 3$. *Compared with control, $P < 0.05$. #Compared with DDP, $P < 0.05$.

Discussion

Cisplatin (DDP) remains a cornerstone chemotherapeutic agent for multiple malignancies; however, its clinical utility is constrained by two critical limitations: cumulative organ toxicity and acquired chemoresistance mechanisms (Zon and Bednarek 2023). Emerging combination therapies aimed at overcoming these limitations have shown promise by synergistically enhancing the apoptotic efficacy of DDP while reducing its systemic burden (Abadi et al. 2022; Rahimi et al. 2022; Ali et al. 2023). The present study provides mechanistic evidence that triptolide (TPL) potentiates DDP-induced apoptosis in CNE-1 cells through coordinated regulation of Bcl-2 family dynamics and MAPK signaling.

We found that TPL inhibited the growth and proliferation of DDP-treated CNE-1 cells in a time-dependent manner, as determined by MTT assay. Furthermore, DDP-induced apoptosis in CNE-1 cells was enhanced by TPL, as demonstrated by Annexin V/PI and Hoechst 33258 staining. Compared with TPL or DDP alone, low-dose combination treatment with these two agents induced significant pro-apoptotic effects in CNE-1 cells. These findings are consistent with reports describing the synergistic effects of TPL in combination with other chemotherapeutic agents across multiple cancer cell types (Liskova et al. 2022; Feng et al. 2024; Liu et al. 2025).

Members of the Bcl-2 family, including Bcl-2/Bcl-XL and Bax/Bak, modulate mitochondrial processes associated with apoptotic cell death by regulating cytochrome c release. The ratio of anti- to pro-apoptotic proteins (Bcl-2/Bax) has been identified as a direct determinant of cell fate (survival or death) in multiple tumor cell lines by influencing cellular sensitivity to apoptotic stimuli (Czabotar et al. 2014). In this study, the Bcl-2/Bax ratio was significantly decreased following treatment with TPL and DDP, which may partially explain their observed synergistic effects. Consistent with our findings, TPL has been reported

to act as a pro-apoptotic agent in renal cell carcinoma by downregulating the Bcl-2/Bax ratio (Li et al. 2011).

Bcl-2 phosphorylation is regulated by ERK1/2, p38, and JNK signaling pathways (Lei et al. 2002; Wagner and Nebreda 2009; Pua et al. 2022; Zhou et al. 2025). Mechanistically, TPL has been shown to suppress DDP-induced p53 transcriptional activity, thereby promoting apoptosis through activation of JNK and Bax in urothelial cancer cells (Matsui et al. 2008). In the present study, treatment with TPL and DDP significantly increased phosphorylation of ERK1/2 and JNK, but not p38, indicating that TPL exerts synergistic effects with DDP primarily through activation of ERK and JNK signaling pathways. This selective pathway activation is consistent with previous reports demonstrating that TPL-induced inhibition of tumor proliferation requires ERK and JNK activation (Miyata et al. 2005; Qin et al. 2018; Liu et al. 2019; Bao et al. 2024), but differs from findings in osteosarcoma and cervical cancer models (Qin et al. 2018; Qin et al. 2018). Notably, although ERK and JNK were strongly activated by combined TPL and DDP treatment, p38 phosphorylation remained unchanged. Further studies are required to elucidate the molecular basis of this selective pathway engagement.

In esophageal squamous cell carcinoma, TPL enhanced DDP sensitivity both *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Liu et al. 2025). Similar chemosensitizing effects have been observed in lung and breast cancer models, in which TPL or its analogs block AKT signaling, downregulate anti-apoptotic proteins, and interfere with DNA repair mechanisms (Zhang et al. 2019; Wu et al. 2023). The ability of TPL to sensitize tumor cells to DDP has important clinical implications. Pre-clinical studies have shown that combining TPL with DDP not only enhances tumor cell apoptosis but also allows for lower doses of chemotherapeutic agents, potentially reducing systemic toxicity (Huang et al. 2019; Zhong et al. 2021). Importantly, TPL and its derivatives have demonstrated efficacy in animal models without increasing toxicity to nor-

Figure 6. The schematic graph that demonstrates the effects and mechanism of triptolide.

mal tissues, and novel delivery systems, e.g., nanoparticles and micelles, are being developed to further improve safety and therapeutic index (Feng et al. 2024; Li et al. 2024). Early clinical investigations of TPL analogs, such as Minnelide, have shown promising results in terms of efficacy and manageable side effects (Borazanci et al. 2024). These advances support TPLs potential as a chemosensitizer in combination therapies, offering new avenues for treating resistant cancers and reducing chemotherapy toxicity.

While our *in vitro* findings provide valuable mechanistic insights, several limitations must be acknowledged regarding their translation to *in vivo* and clinical contexts. First, this study was conducted exclusively in the CNE-1 cell line, an *in vitro* model lacking the complexity of the *in vivo* tumor microenvironment (e.g., stromal interactions, immune infiltration, and drug metabolism), which may impact translational relevance. Additionally, the absence of *in vivo* validation (e.g., xenograft models) means that the observed synergistic effects and systemic safety of the TPL-DDP combination remain unconfirmed.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates for the first time that TPL cooperates with DDP to induce cellular apoptosis by downregulating the Bcl-2/Bax ratio and promoting ERK1/2 and JNK phosphorylation (Fig. 6). Clinically, the synergistic pro-apoptotic effects of the TPL-DDP combination offer a potential strategy to overcome DDP resistance. Notably, this study was limited to *in vitro* cellular experiments; further *in vivo* studies are needed to confirm its safety and efficacy.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Shuxia Li <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-4165-1710>

Data availability

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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